

Polarized intensity (mJy beam⁻¹)

0.3

0.4

0.5

0.6

14 $z_{\text{sp}}=0.13455$

53°36'30"

00"

35'30"

00"

100 kpc

16^h12^m45^s42^s 39^s 36^s

RA (J2000)

Dec (J2000)

